

A Study of the Historical Development of China's First-Rich Strategy: Historical Exploration Based on the Perspective of China's Reform and Opening-up Social Context

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Abstract: Since China's reform and opening up in the 1980s, nearly three decades of economic development have given Chinese society a strong economic force. The use of the strategy of the "first rich" is a key factor in the strengthening of the economy, and many scholars in China have studied the economic aspects of the reform and opening-up policy to varying degrees, but the history of the development of the strategy of the "first rich" is almost blank under the existing research. The biggest difference between this paper and the existing research lies in the discussion of the historical background of the development of the doctrine of the first rich, in addition to the historical development of the Chinese society at that time also made little mention of the historical development. Although this paper is based on the historical development of the strategy of the doctrine of the first rich in China, the actual elaboration of the paper is based on the unique political environment of Chinese society. The exploration of China's problems can not be separated from the unique political attributes of China, although we often say that "if you want to understand a country's economy, you should understand the changes in the world economy", but for Chinese society, it is necessary to add to the political basis of the Chinese society to explore the political attributes of the exploration may be closer to the political attributes of the benchmark to understand the pace of development of Chinese society. A search based on political attributes may be closer to an understanding of the pace of development of Chinese society.

Keywords: The Doctrine of the First Rich, Historical Background, Chinese Politics, Reform and Opening Up, Social Development.

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1 Introduction

Since the founding of the People's Republic of China in 1949, and after the implementation of the reform and opening-up policy in the 1980s, the People's Republic of China has come to the position of the world's second largest economy in less than a century. In the social wave of rapid economic development, the theory of the first rich and the theory of the rich in common have always played an important role in the development of Chinese society as a theoretical politicised social collective consciousness, whether it is the consciousness of the first rich at the beginning of the reform and opening up policy or the consciousness of the rich in common that has been pursued by the Chinese society through the change of time, both of them are playing important theoretical and conscious guiding roles. But what is the actual development of Chinese society under the collective consciousness shaped by the Chinese government? What is the historical background for the emergence of the "first to be rich

theory"? It seems that all the information we have received from the existing sources is positive information about the results of the Chinese government's actions, but there is little mention of the historical background and the motives of the government's actions. At the same time, the question arises: Is it possible that the background of the "first to be rich theory" is not the historical development simply described in the available information? Is it possible that the Chinese people's wealth-based standard of living has really reached the position of well-off? Is it possible that the theory of common wealth is still in the future? In the author's view, only by analysing the true picture of the historical development of Chinese society and understanding the interconnections between events can we better help the people to lead a truly affluent and self-sufficient life, and to realise the true social vision of the theory of communal wealth. Therefore, based on this, the author conducts a research on the historical development of the strategy of the doctrine of the first rich.

2 The historical development of the doctrine of the first rich and the background of the proposal

2.1 Background of the historical development of the first-rich doctrine

2.1.1 Background of the origin of the first-rich theory

Since the founding of New China in 1949, one of the first major events was the land reform. During the land reform movement, the people were divided into 5 classes, which were called landlords, rich peasants, middle peasants, poor peasants and tenant farmers. Among these five classes, the protection of the middle peasants, the solidarity with the poor peasants and sharecroppers, the defeat of the landlords and the seizure of the rich peasants were the core elements of the agrarian reform movement. Under the influence of Mao Zedong's ideology of opposing the peaceful agrarian reform and advocating the class struggle, the agrarian reform movement, which was based on the mainstream of the class struggle, was rapidly launched in all parts of China. In some historical records, the overthrow of the landlords in the land reform movement is described as the greatest significance of the land reform movement. In addition, after the land reform movement, Chinese society also lost the "squires" who had long existed in history as a bridge between the landlords and the landlords.

One of the obvious changes after the land reform movement, as compared to before, was that peasants who were previously landless were given "their" land. Paradoxically, however, this was in conflict with the People's Communalisation movement that followed. In the People's Communalisation Movement, the peasants who had been given land as a result of the Agrarian Reform Movement lost the right to decide on their own land. In terms of timeline, the land reform movement started in the early 1950s, and by 1952 the principle of "land for those who cultivate it" was basically completed, and in the Chinese central government's foreign propaganda, it was claimed that the land reform movement was basically completed by 1953, with the exception of the ethnic minorities.

In the context of international social development, this timeline is fast and short. It is not only the most representative and important event in the early years of the founding of New China, as claimed by the authors, but also the earliest context in which the strategy of the first-rich theory, as argued by the authors, came into being in the later years. At the same time, however, it is worthwhile for us to pay attention to the question of whether, in the present society, decades after the founding of New China, the earliest affluent social class represented by the word "first" in the theory of the first to be rich will become a new generation of landlords and rich peasants in the future, like the landlords and rich peasants who were struggled against

in the 1850s? What will be the fate of these people in the future? This is the author's current concern, and a puzzle that he has not yet solved.

2.1.2 Evolutionary background of the first rich theory

After the agrarian reform movement in Chinese society, a large number of rural people were given land, and the rural class in China was gradually stabilised. With the psychological and emotional state of the peasants fully satisfied, the central government of China also took advantage of the situation to implement a new policy, "the First Five-Year Plan in 1953 and the People's Communalisation Movement in 1958". "In addition to the internal factors mentioned above, i.e. the continuation of the people's enthusiasm for land reform, there was also an important external factor, i.e. the support of the socialist countries for the CCP at that time.

In order to prevent the capitalisation of the peasants, the Chinese central government chose to accept the Soviet Union's policy of agrarian collectivisation in China, which was also known as the "First Five-Year Plan", and which was used as an example of the good relations between the Chinese central government and the Soviet Union central government at that time. One of the important effects of the "First Five-Year Plan" was the implementation of the three major reforms, i.e. the basic completion of the socialist reforms of individual agriculture, handicrafts, and private industry and commerce, which laid the foundation for the development of socialist industrialisation in the later years of the new China. However, one of the major problems was that the quality of steel was not up to the standard, especially the slogan of catching up with Britain and the United States in terms of steel production, which was raised in the Soviet Union in 1956, which seriously ignored the actual development of the Chinese society at that time, and this was one of the reasons for the tearing apart of the Chinese society in the later years.

Subsequently, the rise of the People's Communalisation Movement in 1958 was also accompanied by the continuation of the problems left behind by the First Five-Year Plan, and the "People's Communalisation" Movement, which was carried out by the central government of China on the basis of the failure to solve the problems left behind by the First Five-Year Plan, was also a result of the failure to solve the problems left behind by the First Five-Year Plan. The "People's Communalisation" campaign, which was carried out by the Chinese central government without properly resolving the problems left behind by the First Five-Year Plan, further accelerated the process of tearing apart the society of the new China. For example, the Three Years' Famine, which resulted in the deaths of tens of millions of people, took place during the People's Communalisation Movement. This series of events not only contributed to the deepening of social disruption in China, but also led to a conflict between the top echelons of the Chinese central government, particularly between Mao Zedong and Liu Shaoqi. In terms of the timeline of the

situation, the "First Five-Year Plan" and "People's Commune" were no longer simply the direction of the central government in the early years of China's founding, but rather the link between the "Cultural Revolution" and the "Cultural Revolution" that followed. It is a series of indexes connecting the subsequent events of the "Cultural Revolution". In addition, these historical events are also the key components that promote the dual attributes of self-help and emergence of the theory of the first rich. On this basis, the author argues that the implementation of the "First Five-Year Plan" and "People's Communalisation" is also an evolutionary stage, or an intermediate process from the perspective of the timeline, that drives the emergence of the doctrine of the prevalence of the rich.

2.1.3 The Peak Context of the Generation of the Doctrine of the First Rich

After the acceleration of the median journey between the First Five-Year Plan and the People's Communalisation, Mao Zedong began to implement the "Three-Line Construction" economically and the "Cultural Revolution" politically. "This phase was also the peak phase of the promotion of the theory of the first rich, as argued by the author. In the "three lines of construction", Mao rejected the initiative of Liu Shaoqi, Deng Xiaoping, Zhou Enlai, Chen Yun, and other leaders of the CCP Central Committee, who advocated focusing on the development of agriculture and light industry to solve the problems of the peasants' food and clothing, and reducing the development of heavy industry, and chose to focus on the development of heavy and military industry, which was the initiative of his own leadership. This move was made in the historical environment of that time. Such a move not only further aggravated the burden of survival of the Chinese peasantry at that time in the historical environment, but also simultaneously increased the instability of the social development of the new China. It is worth noting, however, that Mao Zedong took advantage of the international situation at the time to promote the "three lines of construction" campaign, especially the construction of railway routes such as the Southwest Three Lines and the Northwest Three Lines, which laid the groundwork for local economic development and livelihood exchanges. The construction of railway routes, especially those in the Southwest and Northwest, has paved the way for local economic development and livelihood exchanges in the future.

At the same time, Mao Zedong initiated the "Cultural Revolution", in which Mao Zedong developed personal authoritarianism to its peak, and whether it belongs to the scope of totalitarian politicisation concepts such as "totalitarianism" has yet to be further systematically examined. The question of whether or not it falls within the scope of totalitarian politicisation concepts such as "totalitarianism" has yet to be systematically examined, although this point is not the focus of this paper and is not within the scope of this research, but due to the high degree

of political cleansing attributes of the "Cultural Revolution" movement, and the fact that the "theory of the rich first" is not a part of this paper, it is important to investigate the "theory of the rich first" as well. However, due to the highly political cleansing attributes of the "Cultural Revolution" movement, as well as the Chinese political and historical background factors that cannot be avoided in exploring the "theory of the first to be rich", it will only be briefly mentioned here.

"The "Three Red Flags" and the "Four Clean-ups" were the key elements of the Cultural Revolution that could not be ignored, and they were also important factors that contributed to the polarisation of social division. At the same time, the abnormal death of Liu Shaoqi and the persecution of some leaders of the Chinese central government and social intellectuals further worsened the process of healthy development of the new Chinese society, and China's socio-economic sphere suffered a serious shutdown, and the corresponding degree of social cleavage of the new Chinese society also reached its peak. "It was not until Mao Zedong's death and the purging of the Gang of Four in 1976 that the Cultural Revolution was gradually resolved, and the corresponding development of the theory of the "first rich" reached its final stage before it was formally put forward. The development of the theory of the "first rich" also came to the final stage before it was formally put forward.

In terms of the historical development of the doctrine of the first rich, its formulation was not only a self-help strategy of necessity in the environment, but also an emergence of necessity under the long process of historical fluctuation; the two were intertwined and interlinked, and together they constituted the output elements of the doctrine of the first rich. From the early "Land Reform" to the mid-term "First Five-Year Plan" and "People's Communalisation", to the later "Three-Line Construction" and "Culture and Development", it is also a result of the long historical process of the "first rich" theory. "The above is not only the author's brief description of the background of the era in which he lived, but also his understanding of the fact that "the theory of the first to get rich is not only a self-help strategy, but also a strategy of self-help, which is not possible under the circumstances". The above is not only a brief description of the background of the time, but also an example of the author's support for the dual attributes of the idea that "the doctrine of the first rich was not only a self-help measure necessitated by the circumstances, but also a necessity under the long process of historical fluctuation".

2.2 The Proposition of the Theory of the First Rich

After a period of turbulent social development, the standard of living of the Chinese people was generally low. Whether from the point of view of improving people's livelihood, or from the point of view of guaranteeing the stable development of society, or from the point of view of

integrating China into the international social development, the Chinese society at that time urgently needed to carry out a deep-seated social change. In addition to the historical background described above, the output of the "first rich theory" was the urgent need of the actual situation of Chinese society at that time. Thus, from this point of view, the output of "the doctrine of the first to be rich" was not only a self-help strategy that had to be adopted in the circumstances at that time, but also an emergence under the long process of historical fluctuation.

From 1957 onwards, because of the "left" error in guiding ideology, detached from the actual level of the productive forces of society, blindly pursuing the "one big, two communal" system of ownership, trying to make all people rich at the same time and at the same speed, and "suppressing the rich and giving to the poor" by means of equal distribution, the result was that people's lives were plunged into a state of poverty. The result was that people's lives were plunged into a state of poverty. [Deng Xiaoping pointed out that the fundamental task of socialism was to develop the productive forces, to get rid of poverty gradually, to make the country rich and strong, and to make the people rich. [1]

After the development of the previous historical background process, coupled with the nearly two-year hiatus taken by the leaders of the Chinese Central Government after the end of the Cultural Revolution, the theory of the first rich was finally put forward by Deng Xiaoping on 13 December 1978, at the Central Working Conference of the People's Republic of China (CWC). was first proposed by Deng Xiaoping. In that meeting, Deng Xiaoping said, "In terms of economic policy, I think we should allow some regions, some enterprises, some workers and peasants to earn more and live better first because of their hard work and achievements. If a part of the people live better first, it will inevitably produce a great demonstration force, influencing their neighbours and driving people in other areas and other units to learn from them. In this way, the whole national economy will be made to move forward in waves continuously, so that all the people of all ethnic groups in the country will be able to get rich relatively quickly." [2]

This is the point in time when the "theory of the first to be rich" was first publicly put forward, and it is also the content of Deng Xiaoping's first formulation of the "theory of the first to be rich," a kind of epochal output based on the duality of the social environment and the historical process of development in which he was living at the time.

3 The Role and Counter-Role of the Doctrine of the Pre-rich

3.1 The role of the doctrine of the first rich

3.1.1 Mobilising the enthusiasm of the members of the society

The emergence of the "theory of the first rich" has broken the "egalitarianism" that Chinese society used to promote, and the "pot rice" that prevailed in the early days of the founding of New China, The "planned economy" and the "monist ideology" that prevailed during the early years of the new China are very different, although the "weed theory" advocated by Mao Zedong is essentially different from the "theory of the first rich" advocated by Deng Xiaoping. Although Mao Zedong's "Weed Theory" and Deng Xiaoping's "Theory of the First to be Rich" both stemmed from political demands, they had very different considerations in terms of actual operation and social development needs. In the social process of "egalitarianism", the peasants' motivation to produce was seriously reduced, from willingness to work in the beginning to unwillingness to work, reduced work, refusal to work, which gradually triggered the imbalance of the society and the negative behaviours of the people. The emergence of the "theory of the first to be rich" precisely cured this negative situation, through the first to be rich, the idea of more work, more pay, coupled with the input of the "sense of competition" and the government part of the decentralisation of some of the policy support, the Chinese people began to dare to compete, The Chinese people began to dare to compete and be willing to work, thus promoting the development process of China's reform and opening up. In this process, the use of incentive models not only facilitated the development of China's reform and opening-up policies, but also deepened the security of development possibilities.

"By the end of the Cultural Revolution, Chinese society had developed a highly centralised political system, a highly centralised planned economic system and a highly monolithic ideological and cultural value system. It was difficult for people to obtain appropriate political resources under the current political system, and social subjects were deprived of economic autonomy under the highly centralised planned economy, while the rigid cultural value system also deprived people of the vitality of innovation. In terms of social operation, Chinese society at that time was in the midst of serious malignant operation and abnormal development. The pan-political incentive mechanism, which had played a major role in the history of social operation, also came to an end. Since the Third Plenary Session of the Eleventh Central Committee, Deng Xiaoping has initiated reforms to emancipate the productive forces, develop them, and mobilise the motivation of the members of the society by changing the old economic, political, and ideological and cultural systems. This objectively puts forward the task of innovating the incentive mechanism of social operation, and the benefit-oriented incentive model has become the new content of the incentive mechanism of social operation in China in the new period." [3] According to the above excerpts from the article by Zhang Yongguang and Mao Jianru in the article "Theoretical Innovation of the Ideology of Social Incentives - A Review of the Deng Xiaoping According to Zhang Yongguang and Mao Jianru in "Theoretical Innovation of Social Incentive Thought - New

Thoughts on Deng Xiaoping's "Theory of the First to be Rich", we can also see that the "Theory of the First to be Rich", in terms of the mass base on which the policy is to be implemented, has become the most important social incentive mechanism in the world. Through its own value advantage, "the theory of the first to be rich" not only influences and stimulates the positive psychology of the members of the society to master the right of autonomy and become rich, but also makes the members of the society transform into practical actions under the influence of the positive psychology and emotion.

3.1.2 The role of the promotion of social development

Society is an extremely complex system, its normal operation or benign operation requires a series of internal and external conditions, its vitality, power comes from a good social operation incentive mechanism. Social operation incentive mechanism is the incentive mechanism into the whole process of social operation, long-term, sustained role in order to guide the values and behaviour of its members of the dynamic process. [4]

"The "theory of the first to be rich" is like a key to a new world, opening the door to the reform and opening up of Chinese society. Although the "theory of the first rich" focuses on the economic prosperity of the members of the society, it has a radiating effect, but it affects, and even promotes the development of Chinese society in many aspects, for example, the establishment of the stock market, the development of stockholders, the inflow of international capital, the prevalence of investors; for example, the development of the private economy, the reform of the state-owned enterprises, the prevalence of self-employed people, the rise of the freelance profession; for example, the financial system, the reform of the state-owned enterprises, the prevalence of self-employed people, the rise of freelance professions. rise; for example, the construction of the financial system, the establishment of the regulatory system, the diversification of industry attributes, and the diversification of employment positions for members of society; and, the continuous improvement of the legal system, and the output and development of multiple fields; and so on. All of these demonstrate the positive changes brought to Chinese society and the positive influence brought to the international community by the "first to be rich theory" of the reform and opening-up policy. As a result, the economic strength of the Chinese central government and the standard of living of the people have changed markedly compared with those before the reform and opening-up policy.

3.1.3 Paving the way for later national construction

Taking "point, line and surface" as its strategic layout, from special economic zones to coastal areas to inland areas, China's reform and opening-up process was a gradual development process, and the Chinese central government at that time reduced the elements of "political extremism" and "policy integration", and chose to take moderate steps. "This

is not only the logic behind Deng Xiaoping's concept of "the theory of the first rich", but also, in the author's view, an extremely important factor in the positive development of the "theory of the first rich". This is not only the logical system behind Deng Xiaoping's concept of "the theory of the first rich", but also part of what the author considers to be the most important factor in the positive development of the theory. From the perspective of China's later economic development, the reform and opening-up policy implemented in the 1980s has been a key factor in the development and enhancement of the Chinese economy in many ways. Without the early "point, line, surface" strategic layout, there may not be today's Chinese socio-economic development, and this is also the author's current advocate of the "first to be rich theory" for China's later construction of the early paving role, whether it be Whether it is the smooth development of the Shenzhen Special Economic Zone in the early days, or the accession to the 'WTO' at the beginning of the 21st century; whether it is the growing development of the coastal areas, or the gradual changes in the inland areas; whether it is the layout of a number of experimental zones to carry out, or the possibility of the future development of China's economy, the implementation of the "Theory of the First to be Rich", the "Theory of the First to be Rich". Whether it is the gradual development of the coastal areas or the gradual changes in the inland areas; whether it is the layout of several experimental areas or the possibility of future economic development in China, the implementation of the "doctrine of the first to be rich" and the strategic layout of "points, lines and surfaces" are the basic elements of the construction and development of the Chinese society in the early days, and they play an important role in paving the ground for the long-term development of the Chinese society.

3.2 Counterproductive effects of the theory of the first rich

3.2.1 The prevalence of the two-track system

Under the social wave of reform and opening up, a large number of officials chose to "go into business", although to some extent this accelerated the progress of China's socio-economic development, but it greatly undermined the mobility and spontaneity of the Chinese market. In particular, it has had a destructive effect on socio-political stability, not only seriously increasing social inequality, but also creating an antagonistic situation between the general public and the powerful.

Under the influence of the "dual-track system" and the actual operation of "buying and selling" and "buying low and selling high", the official class, which originally occupied the dominant resources in society, has transformed itself into an organisation that oppresses the lower classes of Chinese society. The official class has transformed itself into a new type of existence that oppresses the people at the bottom of Chinese society. The occupation of resources by the powerful has also further expanded the growth of the

third zone, causing the tearing effect of Chinese society to increase rather than decrease. With the prevalence of the two-track system, various political and economic interest groups have emerged, and up to now in Chinese society, these situations are still playing their respective roles in the interests of Chinese society, either explicitly or implicitly.

3.2.2 Polarisation of the standard of living of members of society

Because of the political guarantees brought about by the "incremental approach" to the "dual-track system," the "dual-track system" once gained momentum, which was the political basis for China's rapid socio-economic development, but also an important factor in the intensification of social fragmentation in China. This was the political basis for China's rapid socio-economic development, but it was also an important factor contributing to the intensification of China's social division. Although the Chinese central government has been promoting "gradualism" as the reason for the success of China's social reform and opening up, the author believes that "incrementalism" is a more important factor, which is one of the differences between this paper and the concepts advocated by existing research.

Although the development of the "dual-track system", under the framework of Deng Xiaoping's "get-rich-quick theory" of gradual enrichment of the whole population, has brought about rapid and incremental significant economic benefits for China's short-term socio-economic development, it has not enabled the grassroots to gain access to development due to the restriction of its focus on the powerful class, and has not enabled the grassroots to gain access to development. However, because the focus of resources is limited to the powerful, and the grassroots have not been able to obtain the external conditions necessary for their development, it has gradually led to a significant gap between the living standards of the members of the society, and even to serious polarisation and fragmentation. This situation has not only not been effectively resolved in Chinese society today, but has instead taken on a more and more malignant appearance. For example, Li Keqiang, the former Premier of the Communist Party of China (CPC) Central Committee, said that hundreds of millions of people still earn less than 1,000 RMB a month, despite the fact that the CPC Central Government claimed to have built a moderately affluent society in all aspects of society. In recent years, China's peasants have seen a dichotomy between the seemingly increasing per capita disposable incomes in urban and rural areas announced by the central government. It is worth noting that the meagre incomes of a large number of people seem to indicate a conflict between the real living standards of China's underclass and the establishment of a moderately affluent society in all aspects. This is part of what the authors see as the threat of further fragmentation and polarisation of Chinese society in the future.

4 Summary of the Theory of the First Rich and Prospects for the Theory of Common Wealth

4.1 Summary of the Theory of the First Rich

The emergence of the "theory of the first rich", from the point of view of China's central government, has brought great positive effects on the reform and opening up of the Chinese society, both in terms of the rise of the economic assets of the state treasury and the acquisition of the interests of the political power class, which has also produced the effects that the government would like to see in the construction of a harmonious society and the rejuvenation of the nation at a later stage. This is also a positive effect on the construction of a harmonious society and national rejuvenation, which the government wants to see.

At the same time, it should be noted that the emancipation of the mind is the most important thing from the point of view of the right to life of the members of the society. "China is a country deeply influenced by feudalism and small-scale production, with a deep-rooted ideology of 'not suffering from scarcity but from uneven distribution'." This ideology and the 'left' ideology in socialist society are marvellously combined, not only seriously hindering the development of socialist productive forces and the overall progress of socialist society, but also becoming a spiritual shackle on people. For a long time, egalitarianism was mistakenly fixed as the superiority of socialism, differences in wages and incomes were regarded as bourgeois legal rights, and the harsh reality made people talk about 'wealth'. Against this background, Deng Xiaoping's 'theory of the first to get rich' was like a spring thunder, prompting people to free themselves from traditional concepts, to dare to get rich, to get rich, and to get rich became a trend. This undoubtedly gave new impetus and support to the ideological emancipation movement that was underway at the time, and greatly accelerated the process of ideological emancipation." [5] According to the above excerpts from the article "On Deng Xiaoping's "Theory of the First to Get Rich" and Its Relationship to the Theory of a Harmonious Society" by Lv Xiulan and Zhang Kaiju, we can also see that the "Theory of the First to Get Rich" has brought about a positive influence on the rights of the members of the society and has played an important role in the emancipation of the people's minds. We can also see the positive impact of the "theory of the first rich" on the rights of the members of the society, and its important role in the emancipation of the people, which is the most important point of the author's view on the positive impact of the "theory of the first rich" based on the people's own rights.

However, just as a positive aspect is a positive aspect, a negative aspect is also a negative aspect. Based on an objective and rational perspective, we cannot completely ignore the negative effects of the "get-rich-quick theory" just

because of the positive effects of the "get-rich-quick theory". The implementation of the dual-track system is an extremely unfair example. Under the influence of the powerful class, the practice of "buying and selling" has not only enabled the class that has already taken up the advantageous resources of society to obtain more benefits under the policy of "the theory of the first rich", but also made the poor and the disadvantaged at the bottom receive more benefits. It also makes the already impoverished grassroots accept more oppressive practices from the powers that be, and this also makes the gap between the rich and the poor in Chinese society widen and widen. The rich are getting richer and the poor are getting poorer, and the problem of the wealth gap has not been effectively solved until now. On the contrary, in the actual situation of the Chinese society, the problem of the wealth gap has not only fallen into a vicious circle of increasing rather than decreasing, but has also seriously impeded the process of the healthy development of the society. In addition, although the "theory of the first rich" is ostensibly an economic direction, its actual basic point is the consideration of political factors, and therefore, under the wave of reform and opening up of China's central government, members of the community who are unable to clarify the relationship between themselves and the government and the development of the country, then in today's social environment, will be extremely easy to This is also a potential social crisis, especially for the future development of Chinese society.

4.2 Prospects of the Common Wealth Theory

Whether it is Deng Xiaoping's policy of "the theory of the first to get rich" at the beginning of the reform and opening-up period, or Chen Yun's policy of "birdcage economy", which was eliminated by the central government of China at that time, both of them look forward to the vision of a society based on the "theory of shared wealth". The "common wealth theory" is a vision of a society. Xi Jinping's recent promotion of a "moderately prosperous society" is also a visionary manifestation of the "common wealth theory". It is the author's vision, and the direction of his endeavours, to see that all people can live a prosperous life, but equally, we need to be clear about the fact that vision is vision, and reality is reality. It is difficult to judge whether the ultimate goal of communism is a "modern utopia" or not, but from the case of the collapse of the Soviet Union, we should understand that the "Common Wealth Theory" is only a visionary idea, not the actual face of society. Distributive justice has become an important element and embodiment of social justice. It has become the essential provision and inherent requirement of socialism with Chinese characteristics. [6] Although comprehensive well-off does not mean the same and identical well-off for everyone, if the overall living standard of people in poor areas cannot be improved, the completed comprehensive well-off cannot be convincing. [7]

Judging from the historical development of the People's Republic of China since its founding in 1949, there

is no problem for the Chinese Central Government to regard the "common wealth theory" as a beautiful vision, and on the contrary, it may even demonstrate to the outside world that the Chinese Central Government is serving the people. However, it is extremely unrealistic and even dangerous to realise such a beautiful vision in the real world. Whether it is the "big pot rice" or "egalitarianism" practised in the early days of the new China, these are all bloody lessons recorded in history, especially the "three-year disaster", where tens of millions of lives were lost. In particular, the loss of tens of millions of lives in the "Three Years' Disaster" has shown us the lesson that this beautiful vision cannot be realised in the actual society. Therefore, in the current social environment, perhaps we need to rethink the possibility of the future development of Chinese society. There is nothing wrong with the vision of "Common Wealth Theory", but if it is put on hundreds of millions of people and has been a bloody lesson for the implementation of the real society, then "Common Wealth Theory" may no longer be judged by the simple right and wrong.

5 Conclusion

Although most scholars, experts, and politicians believe that Deng Xiaoping's policy of reform and opening up is based on economic strategies, based on the unique political attributes and choices of Chinese society, the author does not believe that the reform and opening up policy is based on Deng Xiaoping's economic strategies, but rather is an extension of the economic reforms that Deng Xiaoping carried out on the basis of his political choices. Therefore, when discussing this issue, the public needs to make a comprehensive and objective analysis, and it is not desirable to be homogenised, nor is it desirable to be fixated.

Although many people believe that the most important reason for the success of the reform and opening-up policy implemented by the Chinese central government is the implementation of the "incremental" strategy, based on a number of factors, the author believes that this claim is not objective, and that it seriously ignores the basic political attributes of Chinese society. It is the "incremental" approach that has contributed to the success of China's reform and opening-up. Throughout the world's development, one thing that reforms have in common is the redistribution of social benefits after collecting the interests of vested interests. This is the most direct manifestation of reform, but this is not the case with China's reform and opening-up. In addition to the dual system and decentralisation, the "gradualism" is more directly related to the "Great Leap Forward", the "Three-Line Construction" and the "Cultural Revolution". Cultural Revolution", which we can see in the initial historical background of this paper as failures and undesirable elements. However, the "incremental approach" is different, and can even be a guarantee of "progressivity", such as the ambiguity of the legal norms of the "incremental approach", the tacit acceptance of certain corruption phenomena, the acceptance

of the interests of the Chinese central government, and the acceptance of the "incremental approach", as well as the "incremental approach". For example, the ambiguity of the legal norms, the acquiescence to certain corruption, and the increase of the central government's own interests all contribute to the further entrenchment of the established power and interest groups. Therefore, the author believes that the "incremental approach" is the fundamental reason for the success of China's reform and opening up, and also the fundamental guarantee for the successful implementation of the "first to be rich theory".

Under the new international order, which is becoming increasingly globalised and universal, the only way for Chinese society to move from the "first rich theory" to the "common wealth theory" is to carry out a truly democratic and pluralistic social change. As a government, we may actively promote political changes, such as legislation on political innovation, financial system, people's rights, social supervision, etc., to give people enough free space and solid legal protection for individuals and the market economy. As a member of the society, we may only break the original perspective of fixed thinking, keep an open and objective mode of thinking, try to pay attention to the basic issues of social politics, try to care about the real life of every compatriot, try to find answers to the questions, and hit the essence from the surface, in order to find and seize the opportunities, and to truly realise the beautiful vision of "the world is the commonwealth, the people are rich together".

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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